

CORRELATION OF LEXICAL-SEMANTIC RELATIONS WITH GRADUONYMY

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Abstract. *The article deals with the phenomenon of graduonymy of semantic relations between words considered within the framework of language systematic relations, which is relevant for today from the point of view of linguistics.*

Keywords: *systematic linguistics, graduonymy, semantic relations between words, lexical paradigm, lexical gradation, synonymy, antonymy, hyponymy, paronymy relations.*

In systematic lexicology and lexical paradigms, combining graduonymic words around the main word (dominant, neutral, moderate) is of practical importance. In the lexical paradigm, the leading word is the center, core of this lexical microsystem, and other words in the content of this lexical microsystem form its various surroundings [Orifjonova Sh, 1996: 39]. The name as the central, nuclear part of the leading word in the graduonymic series is distinguished not only in graded words, but also in sentences. Among today's modern methods, the transformational analysis method aims to transform a complex syntactic whole into different nuclear sentences.

The first ideas about lexical classification were reflected in manuals on lexicology. We can see the first general theoretical interpretation of lexical leveling in H.Ne'matov and R.Rasulov "Fundamentals of Uzbek language system lexicology" [Ne'matov H., Rasulov R, 1995: 29]. At the same time, lexical leveling of conflicts between linguistic units was studied among at least three language units. Uncertainty in the grading system, as is characteristic of language and speech, moves from generality to particularity, and essence becomes a phenomenon. In the linguistic world of a person who is able to understand natural phenomena as they are, lexical-grammatical and paralinguistic tools are combined and combined to create a clear picture of continuous gradation. For example, if lullaby - baby - infant - child - teenager - young man - old man - old man is abstract in the line of linguistic gradation, then the age and condition related to the concept of "boy" are defined only in the spoken state. Just as language and speech acquire generality and specificity, this law also applies in the grading system and covers the levels of language such as phonology, morphology, lexicon, and syntax.

The meaning of the concept of "Graduonymy" within the framework of semantic relations between words is "the decrease or increase of a sign, quantity". It is necessary to understand the phenomenon of gradual decrease and increase between language units. These are paradigmatic, syntagmatic, hierarchical relations.

Graduonymic processes in the semantic relations between words have been studied for many years as part of synonymous processes, until they began to be studied in our linguistics as a separate phenomenon. The meanings of the word in the dictionary are very wide: synonymous, antonymic, graduonymic (meaning gradation), paronymic (whole-piece), funconymic (duty), hierarchonymic (step, big-small) and hypo -it is important that we list hyperonyms. These events are considered a lexical-semantic system that is directly related to each other.

Graduonymy is also part of synonymy, and later it was not differentiated from hypo-hyperonymy. Even today it is difficult to distinguish between them. "Graduonymy is closely connected with hyponymy and sometimes even mixed: child, lullaby, baby, infant. Although the words in this line seem to be united under the hyperonym of child, the semantic relations between the words child, lullaby, baby, baby and the words flower, basil, tulip, and rose are different from each other. This uniqueness requires a separate approach to each of these lexical paradigms. [R. Safarova, Types of lexical-semantic relations, manual, Tashkent teacher - 1996, 21]. Here, the hyperonym of flower is similar to the word child, but tulip, rose, and basil are hyponyms of the genus flower. Also, the words lullaby, baby, and baby form the gradational circle of the word child.

The phenomenon of graduonymy is also distinguished from domestic animals by their age in expressing the names of cows, horses, sheep, and camels. For example, cattle: calf, body, heifer, cow; noun: kulun, tay, gonon, hawthorn, tolon, etc. "Pets play an important role in the daily social life and lifestyle of local residents. Therefore, as a result of distinguishing and naming the different aspects of domestic animals, each of these denotations is differentiated according to the degree of growth. [R.Safarova, Types of lexical-semantic relations, manual, Tashkent teacher - 1996, 27]. This classification of graduonymic words is considered a phenomenon similar to the fact that each of the hyponym words is combined separately to create a hyperonym. In the hyperonym of fish, the classification of its hyponym species, such as pike, carp, and eel, is a similar phenomenon, but they differ from each other. In the framework of zoonyms, the animals that live side by side with man and serve him differ mainly at the level of name. Such names, of course, attract lexical-semantic analysis within the framework of linguistics.

"The subject appears as a complex of certain signs, and the meaning of signs in nouns is an important component of their meaning. Therefore, in the Uzbek language, most specific (concrete) nouns and a number of abstract nouns form graduonymic series. [Sh.Orifjonova, Lexical graduonymy in the Uzbek language, abstract, Tashkent - 1996, 21]. The horse family forms the basis of the ranking system. Object-subject names are mainly gradational. In the world of human linguistics, the concepts of units of the noun group in the range of contradictory meanings exist in the language even if they do not have their own names. Within adjectives, there is a degree and a law of growth between words that have an antonymic relationship with each other. It will be possible to turn it into a graduonymic system by using the middle word between words with opposite meanings. For example, big - medium - small, tall - medium - short, young - medium - old. From the point of view of a person's age, the concepts of maturity, maturity, and a person suffering from life's difficulties are included in the composition of the word middle. When young and old are taken in the opposite sense, we include human infancy, youth, maturity, maturity, maturity, and old age in the stage of gradation. That is, we call it the graduonymic system. Such a lexical ranking system is also found in other word groups pronouns, adverbs, imitative words, and modal words. In particular, graduonymic gradation is very common within the noun group.

The lexeme has a syntagmatic scope when various surrounding semas are gathered in the lexeme. "When the denotative (name), connotative (expression), functional (task) meanings of linguistic word patterns are separated, we need to study and research them separately in the grading system. In the analysis of this type of gradation, the properties of denotations (existence, extralinguistic factors) and the semantic signs of linguistic units are interpreted in an organic relationship. [Odiljon Bazarov, Grading in the Uzbek language, Autoreferat, Tashkent-1997, 27].

The denotative grading system is considered as a product of the existence of fire symbols and the processes associated with them. In this, the three aspects of existence, understanding, and semema are combined. In our speech, it is often not possible to distinguish which denotative meaning is needed in the speech situation instead of the naming and naming of the linguistic word. For example, the spiritual group of lexemes good, orderly, honest, excellent are considered close to each other. Among the concepts of positivity, there is growth and gradation from little to more.

In grammatical and phonological systematic studies, there is a paradigm of learning to name separate syllables of the language. Like consonant paradigm, tense paradigm, complex sentence paradigm. The term paradigm is also used in lexicology to refer to a system of any complexity. (Lexical paradigms, synonymous paradigms). But in lexicology, another (or new) lexical (lexical) series, lexical meaning groups (groups), topic groups, lexical field terms are also used in the lexeme to express different levels of complexity of lexical paradigms. [Orifjonova Sh, 1996: 59]. At this point, it can be said that the concept of paradigm has a very broad meaning and can be used in almost all branches of science. There is a dialectical relationship between each of the above expressions and the term paradigm, that is, a separation in the form of the concepts of generality (paradigm) and specificity (lexical line, lexical semantic group, subject groups, lexical field) is appropriate.

It seems that it is more appropriate to use the term paradigm for synonymy or antonymy relations in relation to the relation of graduonymy. In these types of relations, the paradigmatic aspect is considered to be always present in the human linguistic world. As soon as a word is said It is natural to remember that lexeme in our linguistic mind. In relation to the relation of graduonymy, it is appropriate to call the term paradigm "lexical series" as a placeholder.

In general, graduonymy is a form of emotional relationship that takes place in language in such cases as generality and specificity, incompleteness and completeness, abstraction and precision. Linguistic leveling is an important factor not only of language construction, but also of speech creation. It forms the meanings of exactness - difference - contradiction at the levels from phonology to text in language construction.

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